

CRUK

Data management plan required?	Yes. Researchers applying for funding must include a DMP
RDM policy Link	http://www.cancerresearchuk.org/sites/default/files/cruk_data_sharing_policy_2017_final.pdf
Definition of data	Not specified
Length of data management plan	300 words
DMP template/ requirements	Type of data including amount and format, standards for data collection and management, metadata for appropriate interpretation of results, methods to be used to share data (i.e. third party, directly, with data sharing agreement), restrictions on data sharing (IP, confidentiality etc.)
Required data repository	Not known
Time for data release	Limited, defined period of private use is allowed and no later than acceptance for publication of the main findings.
Time for long-term storage of data	Data should be shared for a minimum of 5 years after the end of the project.
Costings	Archiving, repository, data storage and data management services (must be in line with cost of overall grant)
Last updated	June 2017
Contact Details	Paola.Quattroni@cancer.org.uk
Comments	Data generators and sharers should receive appropriate recognition. (Researchers encouraged to use DOI's or ORCID identifiers). Funder committee will monitor the implementation of the data management plan.

Documents used:

Data sharing FAQs <https://www.cancerresearchuk.org/funding-for-researchers/applying-for-funding/policies-that-affect-your-grant/submission-of-a-data-sharing-and-preservation-strategy/data-sharing-faqs>

Data sharing guidelines <https://www.cancerresearchuk.org/funding-for-researchers/applying-for-funding/policies-that-affect-your-grant/submission-of-a-data-sharing-and-preservation-strategy/data-sharing-guidelines>

CRUK policy on data sharing and preservation

https://www.cancerresearchuk.org/sites/default/files/cruk_data_sharing_policy_2017_final.pdf

Practical guidance for researchers on writing data sharing plans

<https://www.cancerresearchuk.org/funding-for-researchers/applying-for-funding/practical-guidance-for-researchers-on-writing-data-sharing-plans>

Accessed: June 2018